

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Status of iron during radon-sulfide balneotherapy in osteoarthritis patients

Jadwiga Kuciel-Lewandowska¹, Sylwia Płaczkowska^{2*},
Lilla Pawlik-Sobecka³, Agnieszka Piwowar⁴

¹ Department of Physiotherapy, Faculty of Health Science, Medical University of Wrocław, Poland

² Teaching Medical Diagnostics Laboratory, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Wrocław, Poland

³ Department of Professional Training in Clinical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Wrocław, Poland

⁴ Department of Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Wrocław, Poland

*Corresponding author: Sylwia Płaczkowska, Borowska St. 211 A, 50-556 Wrocław, Poland; Telephone: +48 71 7840167; Fax: +48 71 7840154; Email: sylwia.placzkowska@umed.wroc.pl

ABSTRACT

Osteoarthritis and other arthropathies are still one of the most debilitating musculoskeletal disorders among the elderly population. Pathogenesis of these diseases is multifactorial and mainly connected with increasing of oxidative stress. Pharmacotherapy, physico- and balneotherapy are the most commonly used methods of treatment. The mechanism of action balneotherapy in arthropathies is not fully understood. Probably it is a combined effect of used forms of biological interactions which influence different metabolic pathways. One of the potential factor connected with decreasing oxidative stress status during balneotherapy can be iron bioavailability and changes its concentration during this therapy. The aim of this study was assessing change of iron blood status during the routine 21 days' radon-sulfide balneotherapy course in patients with osteoarthritis. The study group consisted of 35 osteoarthritis patients without impediment to comprehensive treatment at spa. The age of patients ranged 32-67 years (average 53.5). The blood samples were collected before the therapy and after 21 days of treatment at a spa. The levels of iron, transferrin, total iron binding capacity and transferrin saturation percent were assessed. Within statistical comparison before and after spa course revealed decreasing trend for all iron status parameters after 21 days' spa treatment, but the observed changes were significant only for TIBC. In the course of spa therapy Osteoarthritis patients, the level of the systemic iron components is not affected and changes in blood oxidative status during this therapy probably are not influenced by iron status and vice versa.

Keywords: Balneotherapy; Iron; Osteoarthritis; Oxidative stress; Radon-sulfide water.

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Kuciel-Lewandowska J, Płaczkowska S, Pawlik-Sobecka L, Piwowar A. Status of iron during radon-sulfide balneotherapy in osteoarthritis patients. *MicroMed*. 2017; 5(2): 63-68.

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1039153>

Received: August 16, 2017

Revised: October 19, 2017

Accepted: October 29, 2017

Copyright: © 2017 Kuciel-Lewandowska J, et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.
www.journals.tmkarpinski.com/index.php/mmed

Transparency declaration: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical considerations: Medical University of Wrocław Ethics Committee (KB-401/2008).

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis and other arthropathies are still one of the most debilitating musculoskeletal disorders among the elderly population. Joint damages characteristic for those diseases mainly occur because of an imbalance between the processes of degeneration and regeneration of articular cartilage structures. Until now many risk factors favoring the development of degenerative joint disease have been identified, such as age, weight, previously sustained traumas to joints, sports, sex and genetic predisposition [1, 2].

The latest scientific reports confirm that the pathogenesis of changes in osteoarthritic joints is complex, occurs on many levels and strictly connected with increase of oxidative stress [3, 4]. In a face of constantly lengthening life expectance, treatment and care for patients with these progressive and irreversible diseases generate large social and economic costs [5].

It is important to introduce effective pharmacological and biological forms of therapy. In some countries, especially in Europe spa therapies and 21-days' curative courses are very popular and have a long tradition in treatment of many rheumatic diseases. One form of adjuvant therapy for patients with osteoarthritis in Poland is a routine 21-days balneotherapy e.g. in Przerzeczyn Zdrój spa resort with using unique, on a European scale, natural curative radon-sulfide waters [6].

Balneotherapy is an important component of arthropathy treatment called also as spa medicine or medical spa therapy. It refers to the therapies that utilize of spa waters, peloid, physiotherapy, kinesiotherapy, therapeutic massage and different forms of hydrotherapy to reduce pain and improving functional mobility.

Biomedical mechanism of action of balneotherapy and physiotherapy in spa is not entirely clear, because the health resort treatment may affect many factors. In spa treatment, there are used different kinds of energies, as well as natural healing materials such as: peat, gas or medicinal water treatment. This type of therapy brings not only local, but general results, and changes the reactivity of the immune system by activating the adaptive responses. Probably all elements of the balneotherapy influence by mechanical, thermal and chemical effect [7] and can activate the changes of different metabolic pathways in human organism [8-10]. It is suggested that all these forms of medicinal spa treatments have also an antioxidant effect proven in *in vitro* and clinical studies [7].

It is believed that the ferric iron status changes are related with oxidative stress in various diseases (metabolic, inflammatory, infection, cancer) as well as disorders of musculoskeletal system. Iron is an important trace element involved in many biochemical reactions essential for maintaining homeostasis and simultaneously takes part in generating of free radicals due to their high volatility redox potential. Free iron particles are sources of reactive oxygen species mainly via Fenton reaction. Both indispensability and their possible toxic effects cause that the concentration and availability of iron ions remains under strict biochemical control [11].

Among other factors, increasing of reactive oxygen species concentration and cellular oxidative stress products is connected with onset and progression of arthropathies [12, 13]. New studies confirm the antioxidant effect of balneotherapy in osteoarthritis patients [14, 15]. However, the mechanisms by which spa therapy influence on oxidative status are still not fully understood. One of potential factor linking these two aspects can be iron bioavailability and changes of its concentration during balneotherapy course.

The aim of this study was assessing changes of iron blood status during the routine 21 days' radon-sulfide balneotherapy course in patients with osteoarthritis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The project was conducted in a health resort Przerzeczyn Ltd. in Przerzeczyn Zdrój, Poland and was approved by the Medical University of Wrocław Ethics Committee (KB-401/2008). The study group consisted of 35 patients (28 women and 7 men) with pain in joints and spine, caused by osteoarthritis and spinal or degenerative disc disease without impediment to comprehensive treatment at a spa. The age of patients ranged

32-67 year (average 53.5). Patients were qualified for treatment by a referring physician and balneologist working as a medical consultant in the spa in accordance with applicable standards. All patients declared voluntary participation in the study in writing; they were also informed about the purpose and protocol of the research. In addition, the study participants declared that during the study they will restrain from taking any vitamin supplements, alcohol consumption and smoking tobacco.

Patients undergoing spa treatment within the 21-days' health resort stays were on the normal diet or highly digestible diet, which was dominated by dishes cooked with low fat content. Both diets were norm calories diets. The main element of therapy accounted for treatments using medicinal radon-sulfide baths. Patients were also prescribed a series of 10 treatments of various types of therapy depending on the needs and type of disease. A sample set of patient treatments used at spa resort included radon-sulfide baths, peat wraps, therapeutic individual and group exercises, laser biostimulation, interference currents.

Table 1 presents the content of the individual components characteristic for Przerzeczyn-Zdrój curative waters.

Table 1. The results of physicochemical studies performed on 24.04.2008 at source of medical waters and at mineral spring spa (MSP).

No	Drilling place location	Water temp. in° C	pH	The content of the ingredient in 1 dm ³ of water			
				H ₂ S Mg	HCO ₃ Mg	Rn Nci	Rn Bq
1.	Borehole No. II	12.0	7.62	1.96	263.2	2.21	81.8
2.	Borehole No. IX	12.0	7.72	1.70	289.6	1.71	63.3
3.	MSP tank	16.0	7.65	1.87	277.9	2.20	81.4

The blood samples were collected from patients by venipuncture before the therapy and after 21 days of treatment at the spa resort. The level of iron was measured by Feren S method, transferrin by immunoprecipitation method, total iron binding capacity (TIBC) by the Unsaturated Iron Binding Capacity (UIBC) method and transferrin saturation percent were calculated. All reagents were supplied from DiaSys, Holzheim, Germany and laboratory tests were determined using Konelab 20i biochemical analyser (ThermoScientific, Vantaa, Finland). The results were analyzed statistically, by the Wilcoxon test for related data using STATISTICA12.PL. The values of $p < 0.05$ were regarded as significant.

RESULTS

Results of iron status parameters before (start point) and after 21 days' spa therapy (end point) are given as median, Q₁-Q₃ range and min.-max. values in Table 2.

The study showed that medians and range of Q₁-Q₃ quartiles nearly all iron status parameters, except of transferrin concentration, were in the reference value ranges in both estimated points. However, the minimum and maximum values of the iron, transferrin concentration and transferrin saturation were located both above and below references cut points. Only for TIBC we found all statistical descriptors inside references values bounds. Statistical comparison before and after spa course reveled decreasing trend for all iron status parameters after 21 days' spa treatment. The iron, TIBC and transferrin concentration declined by 7.7 %, 4.9 %, 9.1% respectively, and transferrin saturation by 3.9 %. Observed changes were significant only for TIBC ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the examined parameters before and after balneotherapy course.

Parameters	N	Start point median (Q ₁ -Q ₃) (min.-max.)	End point median (Q ₁ -Q ₃) (min.-max.)	p value
Iron [μmol/l] Reference value: 10.6-28.3	35	18.2 (13.6-24.0) (6.7-38.0)	16.8 (12.1-21.0) (6.6-32.0)	0.317
TIBC [μmol/l] Reference value: 44.8-73.4	35	54.4 (51.0-60.1) (46.7-69.3)	52.1 (49.2-57.4) (50.0-66.9)	0.014
Transferrin saturation [%] Reference value: 20-50	35	33.5 (26.7-39.9) (14.4-54.9)	32.2 (24.6-36.6) (13.7-47.9)	0.650
Transferrin [g/l] Reference value: 2.0-3.6	35	3.3 (2.5-4.1) (1.0-5.7)	3.0 (2.3-3.9) (1.1-5.4)	0.342

DISCUSSION

In the scientific literature, there are few reports about the using of natural medicinal resources like water and muds as a form of therapy. Their use is more popular in countries that have large resources and long tradition of use spa therapy. Such forms of therapy are of great interest and readily used in many old spa resorts located in different areas of Poland. Balneotherapy and physiotherapy are established adjuvant methods used in osterarthritis treatment [16]. Spa therapy, by influence on systemic changes, seems to be important factor in management of these diseases. We revealed in our previous investigation, that spa therapy and outpatient treatment reduce the level of pain in patients with degenerative joints and disc disease. What interesting, the reduction of pain level was more effective in case of therapy conducted in the spa [6]. Moreover, our unpublished study has shown significant increase in blood antioxidant status of patients' underling 21-days balneotherapy in Przerzeczyn Zdrój resort.

In presented study, we investigated iron status parameters before and after routine 21 days' radon-sulfide spa treatment because of importance of iron in the oxidant/antioxidant balance.

Among examined parameters we observed significant decrease only in Total Iron Binding Capacity. The remaining parameters of iron status showed only decreasing trend. Despite the fact significant shift for TIBC before and after balneotherapy, in our opinion all this difference due to the small degree of values change, seems to be not important in clinical practice. In available literature, we found only single studies in similar area to our research. Jokic et al. in 2010 have showed that sulphur baths and mud packs application during 21-days' spa treatment influenced hematological blood parameters and caused an increase in: number of circulating red blood cells, mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) and decrease in lipid peroxidation in plasma [15]. But in their study iron status parameters during spa therapy were not investigated. Findings, for iron metabolism, similar for observed in our study, were published only by Olah et al. [17]. In overweight and hypertensive participants, they observed changes transferrin, but not iron and C-reactive protein concentration after spa therapy. They did not also find changes in antioxidant status [17]. Based on obtained by us results, we can conclude that in the course of routine 21-day spa therapy in patients with disorders of the musculoskeletal system the level of the systemic iron components is not affected. Probably changes in blood oxidative status during this kind of therapy are not influenced by iron status and vice versa. It is worth to notice there are only a few publications about influence of balneotherapy on antioxidative/oxidative balance and the mechanisms regulating antioxidant capacity, especially about iron status and its contribution to this state [15, 18, 19].

Taking to the account only preliminary character of our study and limited number of participants it is appropriate to continue research in this area for examination exact ways of influence of radon-sulfide balneotherapy and role of iron in the network of metabolic disturbances in osteoarthritis patients.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

JKL conceived the idea for and designed the study, were involved in data collection and performed the research. SP, AP, LPS analyzed the data, conducted the literature search, study selection and prepared manuscript. SP, LPS, IK, AP revised the manuscript for final submission. The final manuscript was read and approved by all authors.

REFERENCES

1. Gonçalves RS, Cabri J, Pinheiro JP. Evaluation of patient characteristics as predictors of health status in knee osteoarthritis patients referred for physical therapy. *Acta Reumatol Port.* 2011; 36(2): 137-144.
2. Vasilic-Brasnjevic S, Marinkovic J, Vlajinac H, Vasiljevic N, Jakovljevic B, Nikic M. Association of body mass index and waist circumference with severity of knee osteoarthritis. *Acta Reumatol Port.* 2016; 41: 226-231.
3. Chojnacki M, Kwapisz A, Synder M, Szemraj J. Osteoarthritis: etiology, risk factors, molecular mechanisms [in Polish]. *Postepy Hig Med Dosw.* 2014; 68: 640-652.
4. Kuciel-Lewandowska J. Balneofizjoterapia a przemiany wolnorodnikowe i ogólnoustrojowe. *Piel Zdr Publ.* 2014; 4(4): 377-382.
5. Czyzewska A, Glinkowski WM, Walesiak K, Krawczak K, Cabaj D, Gorecki A. Effects of preoperative physiotherapy in hip osteoarthritis patients awaiting total hip replacement. *Arch Med Sci.* 2014; 10(5): 985-991.
6. Kuciel-Lewandowska J, Paprocka-Borowicz M. The impact of the spa therapy on reduction of the perception of pain intensity in patients with degenerative joints and disc disease [in Polish]. *Pomeranian J Life Sci.* 2015; 61(3): 257-262.
7. Fioravanti A, Cantarini L, Guidelli GM, Galeazzi M. Mechanisms of action of spa therapies in rheumatic diseases: what scientific evidence is there? *Rheumatol Int.* 2011; 31(1): 1-8.
8. Kloesch B, Liszt M, Krehan D, Broell J, Kiener H, Steiner G. High concentrations of hydrogen sulphide elevate the expression of a series of pro-inflammatory genes in fibroblast-like synoviocytes derived from rheumatoid and osteoarthritis patients. *Immunol Lett.* 2012; 141(2): 197-203.
9. Branco M, Rego NN, Silva PH, Archanjo IE, Ribeiro MC, Trevisani VF. Bath thermal waters in the treatment of knee osteoarthritis: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2016; 52(4): 422-430.
10. Fioravanti A, Giannitti C, Cheleschi S, Simpatico A, Pascarelli NA, Galeazzi M. Circulating levels of adiponectin, resistin, and visfatin after mud-bath therapy in patients with bilateral knee osteoarthritis. *Int J Biometeorol.* 2015; 59(11): 1691-1700.
11. Lipiński P, Starzyński RR, Styś A, Gajowiak A, Staroń R. Heme metabolism as an integral part of iron homeostasis [in Polish]. *Postepy Hig Med Dosw.* 2014; 68: 557-570.
12. Ziskoven C, Jager M, Zilkens C, Bloch W, Brixius K, Krauspe R. Oxidative stress in secondary osteoarthritis: from cartilage destruction to clinical presentation? *Orthop Rev (Pavia).* 2010; 2(2): e23.
13. Baskol G, Demir H, Baskol M, Kilic E, Ates F, Karakukcu C, Ustidal M. Investigation of protein oxidation and lipid peroxidation in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Cell Biochem Funct.* 2006;24(4):307-311.
14. Karagülle M, Kardeş S, Karagülle O, Dişçi R, Avcı A, Durak I, et al. Effect of spa therapy with saline balneotherapy on oxidant/antioxidant status in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a single-blind randomized controlled trial. *Int J Biometeorol.* 2016; 61(1): 169-180.
15. Jokic A, Sremcevic N, Karagulle Z, Pekmezovic T, Davidovic V. Oxidative stress, hemoglobin content, superoxide dismutase and catalase activity influenced by sulphur baths and mud packs in patients with osteoarthritis. *Vojnosanit Pregl.* 2010; 67(7): 573-578.
16. Bender T, Balint G, Prohaszka Z, Geher P, Tefner IK. Evidence-based hydro- and balneotherapy in Hungary - a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Biometeorol.* 2014; 58(3): 311-323.

17. Olah M, Koncz A, Feher J, Kalmanczhey J , Kálmánczhey J, Oláh C, Nagy G, Bender T. The effect of balneotherapy on antioxidant, inflammatory, and metabolic indices in patients with cardiovascular risk factors (hypertension and obesity)--a randomised, controlled, follow-up study. *Contemp Clin Trials*. 2011; 32(6): 793-801.
18. Ekmekcioglu C, Strauss-Blasche G, Holzer F, Marktl W. Effect of sulfur baths on antioxidative defense systems, peroxide concentrations and lipid levels in patients with degenerative osteoarthritis. *Forsch Komplementarmed Klass Naturheilkd*. 2002; 9(4): 216-220.
19. Costantino M, Giuberti G, Caraglia M, Lombardi A, Misso G, Abbruzzese A, et al. Possible antioxidant role of SPA therapy with chlorine-sulphur-bicarbonate mineral water. *Amino Acids*. 2009; 36(2): 161-165.